

UZBEK OPERA IN A MUSIC LESSON IN A COMPREHENSIVE SCHOOL AND ITS ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS

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Annotation. In the article the methods of development of cognitive activity open up students at a study difficult musical genre-opera. determination of cognitive creative activity of students, the pedagogical situations sent to perfection of cognitive and creative capabilities of schoolchildren on material of modern classic Uzbek music open up.

Key words: cognitive activity, students, Uzbek opera, historical and cultural background, activation, the relationship between theory and musical knowledge, creativity, pedagogical situations, cooperation, interdisciplinary connections, pedagogical conditions.

Improving the education system is today a priority task of the policy of our state. The leading idea of transformations is the introduction of modern methods and technologies that comprehensively influence the formation of an active, independent, creative, responsible and purposeful personality, able to successfully fulfill social status and professional roles in today's dynamically developing world.

In the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the strategy of action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" UP-4947 dated February 7, 2017, "On measures to educate physically healthy, spiritually and intellectually developed youth, to raise the system of its education to a qualitatively new level" ПҚ-3907 dated August 14, 2018, SZ, N 33, art. 677 [1,2], emphasizes the idea of increasing the importance of the formation of creative abilities, cognitive activity and independence, the ability to make non-standard decisions, which is associated with new social conditions that require the individual as a future citizen and specialist to be competitive, quickly adapt to changing social, cultural, material, professional conditions.

An analysis of the practice of teaching the subject "Musical Culture" shows that the attitude of teachers to the process of forming the cognitive activity of students is generally positive, but this process is not given due attention. Preference is

given to the work of traditional methods, means and forms of teaching, which does not allow the full use of the developing possibilities of music as an educational subject in the process of forming cognitive activity and independence of students. Therefore, targeted work is needed in this regard.

Cognitive activity and independence is a special complex personal integral education, which includes the formation of goal-setting processes, a complex of positive motives, the synthesis of knowledge, skills, positive emotions, a developed will, reflexive self-government and effective mechanisms of self-regulation and is expressed in a steady desire for self-education [7].

Managing student activity is traditionally called activation. The main goal of activation is to form the activity of students, improve the quality of the educational process. It can be defined as a constantly ongoing process of encouraging energetic, purposeful learning, overcoming passive and stereotyped activity.

Pedagogical practice uses various ways of activation, the main among them is a variety of forms, methods, teaching aids, the choice of such combinations of them, which, in situations that arise, stimulate the activity and independence of students.

The formation of cognitive activity and independence of students is of particular importance in the study of opera as a complex synthetic musical genre, the development of which involves a certain amount of independent cognitive activity of students.

M. Ashrafi's opera "Dilorom" provides rich material for the development of cognitive activity of students in the lesson of musical culture for a number of reasons.

The opera itself, as the most complex synthetic genre of musical art, has an extensive informational, spectacular, musical-aesthetic, dramatic, and emotional field. The presence in the opera "Dilorom" of the inextricable connection between the literary source, the historical basis with the musical embodiment, dramaturgy and images of the performance sets the students the task of comprehensive coverage of this work, which is impossible without the activation of several channels of perception - intellectual, analytical, auditory, visual (video clips, photographs, presentation), associative, creative fantasy.

The opera "Dilorom" is based on a literary source - the poem of the great Uzbek poet Alisher Navoi "Seven Planets", which is included in the famous Five

(Khamsa). The name of the collection was given by Navoi himself, which he interpreted as a hand (panzha), "Panzh ganzh" (five treasures) and the palm of God.

Therefore, students should have an idea (at a level accessible to their age) not only about the content of the Seven Planets, but also about the content of the other four poems:

Confusion of the Righteous (Hayrat ul-Abror, 1483)

Farhad and Shirin (Farhad wa Shirin, 1484)

Layli and Majnun (Layli wa Majnun, 1484)

Seven Planets (Sab'ai Sayyor, 1484)

Wall of Iskandar (Saddi Iskandari, 1485).

The name "Seven Planets" is associated with the symbolic number seven and means seven planets and seven wanderers in the poem. Planets act as patrons of people, their characters and destinies. According to the content of the poem, for Shah Bakhrom, who expelled Dilorom and is painfully experiencing separation from her, his subjects build seven palaces (kasrs) according to the number of days of the week. Seven wanderers tell fairy tale poems every day for the entertainment of the bored Shah [3].

The poem "Seven Planets" has a historical and cultural background, with which it is necessary to familiarize students with a clear understanding of the content of the opera and the era reflected in it, as well as in order to avoid ambiguities and confusion for schoolchildren in the names, characters and time of events.

The hero of the poem "Seven Planets" - Shah Bahram V Gur from the Sassanid dynasty - the king of kings (shahinshah) of Iran, ruled in 420/421 - 438/439.

The dynasty (empire) of the Sassanids is named after Sasan, who was the father of the first king of Pars from the Sassanid clan. This state is also called the New Persian Kingdom, or the Second Persian Empire - an ancient and medieval state that was formed on the territory of modern Iraq and Iran as a result of the coming to power of the Persian Sassanid dynasty. existed from 224 to 651 [5].

Comprehensive familiarization of students with this work is necessary for their penetration into the new meaningful and intonational material of the Uzbek opera.

At the same time, one should be aware that in the lesson of musical culture, the main attention is paid to the musical side of perception and understanding of the studied compositions.

Even the great Al-Farabi expressed the idea that musical practice precedes theory. Theory appears only when the practice has gone all the way of development, when melodies already exist, complete musical compositions, the perception of which is natural. According to the thinker, not only theory and practice in their complementarity constitute the doctrine of music, but also music and poetry exist in musical works in close relationship [4].

Appropriate, in our opinion, is:

- 1) the study of theoretical information by increasing the share of independent cognitive activity of students (books, reference books of musical terminology, encyclopedias, Internet sources);
- 2) analysis and analysis of music in interactive forms of activity in the lesson under the guidance of a teacher.

Listening to fragments of the opera, performing individual themes by the teacher on the piano, gives students the opportunity to get acquainted with a variety of folk oriental melodies (Tajik, Iranian, Indian, Arabic), masterfully used by the composer.

An important point in penetrating into a complex type of operatic art is the teacher's story about such a technique as the inclusion of melodies by the composer from other works in order to more vividly depict the characters' characters and feelings. So, an important role in the characterization of the artist Moni, in love with Dilaram, has an old melody "Karimkul-begi". Moni's story about his misadventures to the sage Nugman is based on the melody "Sarakhbori-navo" from the "Navo" maqom. The aria-reflection of Nugman, who sympathizes with the suffering of poor prisoners (the fifth scene), is based on the melody of the folk song "Ulturgisi" ("Sit with me").

A strong musical, aesthetic and dramatic impression on schoolchildren is made by Dilaram's vocalization, which develops into a song, when Bahram's warriors, subdued by the unusual beauty of the harpist's voice, lower their weapons.

Table 1 shows methods for enhancing cognitive activity by distributing the functions of a teacher and students when studying the theoretical and musical material of the opera "Dilaram".

Development of cognitive activity of 5th grade students in the study of M. Ashrafi's opera "Dilaram"

Table 1

Theoretical information	Analysis of the musical material	Teacher activity	Student activities
Mukhtar Ashrafi and his operas. Opera Dilorom. The origin of opera in Uzbekistan and its further development	Melodism - different image of musical characteristics, borrowing native melodies and samples of developed forms of Uzbek professional music of the oral tradition.	Explains, introduces, with the help of leading questions, finds out the amount of theoretical knowledge and previous musical experience of students	Listen to the teacher's explanation, memorize, ask questions. self familiar rummage in more detail with the biography and work of M. Ashrafi on the basis of the literature indicated by the teacher and independent search. expand knowledge and auditory musical experience by getting acquainted with samples of Uzbek musical creativity of the oral tradition, folk melodies of the peoples of Central Asia

<p>Literary source of the opera. "Five" by A. Navoi</p>	<p>Lyrical and dramatic characteristics of Dilaram and Mani. Mournfully Philosopher Sky aria of Vizier Nug mana</p>	<p>Encourages teaching self-reliant active types of cognitive activity - search-information rational, cultures but-educator through problematic and analytical denmark (statement niya, annotations) on the perception of poetry source ka and opera music</p>	<p>Ask questions about facts and music difficult fragments understanding. Compare a detailed analysis of the plot of the poem and the action of the performance. When listening on your own share the character of the music and its correspondence to the content nyu and characters of heroes. Participate in role-playing games "Poet", "Composer", "Singer"</p>
<p>The historical background of the opera. Sassanid dynasty.</p>	<p>Colorful and melodic yar bone mass and dance scenes</p>	<p>Suggests to draw a parallel with the subject "History"</p>	<p>Perform independent work on the history textbook and other sources</p>
<p>The plot, characters of the opera</p>	<p>The credibility of the musical characteristics of the characters,</p>	<p>Asks to evaluate the music and emotional expressiveness</p>	<p>Conduct a relationship with literature lessons - other works of Uzbek writers lei</p>

		of arias and duets	
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The work carried out allowed us to conclude that the awareness and activity of independent cognitive activity of students in the lessons of musical culture develops under the following pedagogical conditions:

- systematic, purposeful communication with the art of music;
- the presence of interest and value attitude to music;
- the existence of a complex of motives of an aesthetic, artistic, psychological, social, self-affirming, creative nature;
- accessibility of perception;
- the presence of rather difficult educational, cognitive, intellectual tasks.

Further development of the problem is seen in the directions:

- introduction of variable technologies and approaches to the activation of musical, aesthetic, general cultural and cognitive motives and needs of students in the teaching and educational process at the music lesson;
- widespread use of personality-oriented technologies, remote technologies of pedagogical consulting;
- cooperation in a holistic pedagogical process (subject-subject relations, pedagogical interaction, the formation of a psychologically comfortable psychological environment and an atmosphere of creativity);
- involvement of teachers in methodological work in order to form a single technological platform for the formation of students' cognitive activity.

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